

SPECIFIC COURSE OF BACTERIAL CONJUNCTIVITIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN

Ermatova B.O.

Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health

Fergana. Uzbekistan

Abstract. *In pregnant women exposed to metal pollutants (lead, cadmium, zinc), a high incidence of bacterial vaginosis was revealed against the background of an immunodeficiency state. The inclusion of the immunomodulatory drugs Viferon and Kipferon in the course of combination therapy for bacterial vaginosis leads to a pronounced positive clinical effect, which will reduce the incidence of complications of pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period and reduce the risk of intrauterine infection of the fetus.*

Keywords: *pregnancy, bacterial vaginosis, ecology, immunity.*

INTRODUCTION

An increase in unfavorable environmental factors cannot but affect the homeostatic balance of the human body, which ensures the functions of the nervous, endocrine and immune systems. The immunodeficiency states that arise against this background are the pathogenetic basis on which the incidence of nonspecific colpitis, caused by the increased proliferation of mixed anaerobic-aerobic associations of opportunistic microorganisms, has significantly increased [3, 5].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The task of effective treatment of disorders of the vaginal microbiocenosis during pregnancy has not been fully realized. Probably, it cannot be solved with an isolated study of only the vaginal microflora and exclusively local treatment. It seems

advisable to supplement therapy that is effective in sanitizing the genital tract with vaginal dysbiosis with immunocorrection aimed at normalizing impaired immune and interferon statuses. It should be thought that the work should be carried out within the framework of an integrated approach, taking into account disorders in all interested organs and systems [1].

During the examination and treatment, the main group of pregnant women (200 women) was divided into 3 subgroups. The 1st subgroup included 65 pregnant women who received monotherapy with dalacin cream (2% vaginal clindamycin phosphate cream) in the second and third trimesters; in the 2nd subgroup (72 patients) complex treatment with dalacin vaginal cream was prescribed against the background use of the immunomodulatory drug "Viferon". In the 3rd subgroup (63 patients), therapy was carried out using the drug "kipferon", which is a mixture of a complex immunoglobulin drug (60 mg) and human recombinant alpha-interferon (500,000 IU). The drug has antibacterial, antiviral and immunomodulatory properties. Used in the form of rectal suppositories (1x2 times for 10 days).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We studied the content of microelements (lead, cadmium, zinc) in the blood serum of pregnant women with vaginal dysbiosis of the main and control groups living in different ecological zones (Table 1).

Table 1

Content of microelements in blood serum of pregnant women ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$)

Microelements	Control group (n=50)	Main group (n=200)	Reliability coefficient P
Pb	27,3 \pm 2,1	53,2 \pm 1,8	P < 0,001
Zn	320,0 \pm 6,8	760,0 \pm 12,1	P < 0,001
Cu	380,0 \pm 11,6	730,0 \pm 19,5	P < 0,001

Note: P – reliability of the indicators of the main group with the control group.

According to the data obtained, pregnant women living in an area of dangerous metal pollution have a significant ($P < 0.001$) accumulation of heavy metals in the blood. In a comparative analysis of the species composition among strict anaerobes with bacterial vaginosis in pregnant women of the main group, bacteroides (50.1%) and peptostreptococci (22.3%) predominated. Among the bacteroids, *Prevotella melaninogenica* (12.1%, in the amount of 10^7 – 10^9 CFU/ml), *Prevotella bivia* (7.9%, in the amount of 10^5 – 10^7 CFU/ml) were identified. The subsequent positions were occupied by propionobacteria and peptococci with almost equal frequency (Table 2).

Table 2

Species and quantitative composition of anaerobic microflora in pregnant women of the main group

Type of bacteria	Number of strains		Number of microbes (CFU/ml)
	Abs.	%	
<i>Prevotella bivia</i>	56	7,9	10^5 – 10^7
<i>Prevotella melaninogenica</i>	86	12,1	10^7 – 10^9
<i>Bacteroides</i> sp.	142	20,1	10^5 – 10^7
<i>Fusobacterium</i> sp.	29	4,1	10^4 – 10^6
<i>Veillonella</i> sp.	23	3,2	10^4 – 10^6
<i>Peptococcus</i> sp.	48	6,8	10^5 – 10^7
<i>Lactobacillus</i> sp.	35	4,9	10^2 – 10^3
<i>Peptostreptococcus</i> sp.	157	22,3	10^4 – 10^6
<i>Bifidobacterium</i> sp.	23	3,2	10^2 – 10^3
<i>Eubacterium</i> sp.	17	2,4	10^4 – 10^6
<i>Propionibacterium</i> sp.	46	6,5	10^4 – 10^6
<i>Streptococcus anaerobius</i>	28	3,9	10^4 – 10^6
<i>Streptococcus microaerophilis</i>	18	2,6	10^3 – 10^5
Total strains 708 (100%)			

In newborns of the 1st subgroup, respiratory distress syndrome was noted in 19 cases (12.3%), intrauterine growth retardation syndrome - in 8 (5.2%), chronic intrauterine fetal hypoxia occurred in 24 (15.6%) cases. At the same time, in newborns of the 2nd and 3rd subgroups, respiratory distress syndrome was observed in 6 and 2 cases (4.3% and 1.2%, respectively), chronic intrauterine fetal hypoxia was diagnosed in 14 and 9 cases (10.1% and 5.1% respectively). Analysis of the

frequency of the disease in children of the studied subgroups also revealed that in the 2nd and 3rd subgroups there were significantly fewer children with infectious and inflammatory diseases than in the 1st subgroup, respectively 17 (11.1%) and 26 (16.9%), which apparently is a consequence of a decrease in adaptive capabilities in newborns.

CONCLUSION

Thus, thanks to the combined use of the immunomodulatory drugs Viferon and Kipferon, a pronounced therapeutic effect is achieved in the treatment of vaginal dysbiosis in pregnant women exposed to environmentally unfavorable factors.

REFERENCES

1. Gomberg M.A. The use of lactic acid to normalize the vaginal microflora // *Obstetrics and Gynecology*. – 2014. – No. 9. – P. 118–122.
2. Raqiboyevna, G. M. (2023). Hereditary Pigmentary Degeneration. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*, 1(10), 146-149.
3. Ermatova, B. O., & Gazizova, L. K. (2023). RELEVANCE OF OPEN ANGLE GLAUCOMA IN ELDERLY PEOPLE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(21), 26-31.
4. Abdurahim o'g'li, Q. A., & Komilovna, G. L. (2023). IKKILAMCHI KATARAKTANI DAVOLASHDA YAG-LAZER KAPSULOTOMIYA USULI SAMARADORLIGI VA ASORATLARINI BAHOLASH. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 23(3), 26-30.
5. Gazizova, L. K., & Ermatova, B. O. (2023). SOME ASPECTS OF AGE-RELATED MACULAR DEGENERATION. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(13), 28-34.

6. Uralovna, B. Z., & Ravshan o'g'li, A. Y. (2023). Hozirgi o'zbek she'riyatida badiiy ko'chimlarning obyektiv va subyektiv asoslari. *Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 2(2), 9-15.
7. Uralovna, B. Z. (2023). The Place of the Uzbek Language in the World Community. *Genius Repository*, 25, 35-37.
8. Kaipbergenova, S. (2024). APPROACHES IN COMPUTER LINGUADIDACTICS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES. *Models and methods in modern science*, 3(1), 255-257.
9. FAYZULLAEVA, S. U. THEMATIC DIRECTIONS OF THE NATURE OF THE LYRICAL EVENING. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (5), 157-159.
10. Isakovna, I. R. (2023). LITERARI THE ROLE OF IMAGE ENHANCEMENT TECHNIQUES IN THE PROGRESS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(07), 48-52.
11. Georges O.N., Mirzabalaeva A.K. New possibilities of immunomodulatory therapy for chronic genital candidiasis // *Obstetrics and Gynecology*. – 2010. – No. 6. – P. 60–84.